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Presentation to WWRF

Development of ITU-R Regulations,
Recommendations and Reports For
Terrestrial IMT and the Satellite
Component

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What is ITU

ITU is the United Nations'
**specialized agency for information
and communication technologies**
(ICTs)

Enabling a
connected world

ITU Functions and Membership

ITU Structure

Committed to
Connecting the World

3
Sectors

ITU Radiocommunication
Coordinating radio-frequency spectrum and **assigning** orbital slots for satellites

ITU Standardization
Establishing global standards

ITU Development
Bridging the digital divide

Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R)

The **ITU-R** manages the international radio-frequency spectrum and satellite orbit resources and develops standards for radiocommunication systems with the objective of ensuring the effective use of the spectrum. The ITU-R does its work through:

- World Radiocommunication Conference (WRC)
- Radiocommunication Assembly (RA)
- Radiocommunication Study Groups (SG)
- Radio Regulation Board (RRB)
- The Radio Advisory Group (RAG)
- Radiocommunication Bureau (BR)

Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R)

- Objective is to ensure interference free communication through the implementation and the efficient and timely update of the:
 - Radio Regulations and
 - Regional Agreements.

Objective

- Developing and updating international regulations on the use of spectrum and associated orbits
- Applying these regulations and managing the MIFR
- Developing and adopting standards and best practices on the use of orbit/spectrum resources
- Disseminating information on these regulations, standards and best practices

Role/Duties

Radio standardization also establishes '*Recommendations*' intended to assure the necessary performance and quality in operating radiocommunication systems, and seeks ways and means to conserve spectrum and ensure flexibility for future expansion and new technological developments.

ITU-R and BR Structure

ITU
RADIO-
COMMUNICATION
SECTOR

Radiocommunication Assembly (RA)

ITU
RADIO-
COMMUNICATION
SECTOR

The Administrative body for the ITU-R, the RA's duties include:

- Establishing structure and mandates for ITU-R Study Groups
- Adopting ITU-R Study Questions
- Establishing the working methods of the ITU-R
- Electing leadership of ITU-R Study Groups and RAG
- Responding to requests from ITU conferences
- Approving ITU-R Recommendations

RAs are convened every 4 years (Res. 77 PP14), associated in time and place with WRC (the week before)

World Radiocommunication Conferences

ITU
RADIO-
COMMUNICATION
SECTOR

ITU-R Study Groups (SG)

ITU
RADIO-
COMMUNICATION
SECTOR

SG 1: Spectrum management

SG 3: Radiowave propagation

SG 4: Satellite services

SG 5: Terrestrial services

SG 6: Broadcasting service

SG 7: Science services

Coordination Committee for Vocabulary

Conference Preparatory Meeting

* Some WPs meets 2 or 3 times/year; some meetings abroad

Example ITU-R Study Group Structure

Conference Preparatory Meeting

- CPM is one part of the family of ITU-R Study Groups
- CPM prepares a report detailing the technical basis for agenda items being considered by a WRC, including Methods to satisfy the agenda items
- CPM XX-1 is held immediately following a WRC
 - Attended by Chairmen and Vice Chairmen of ITU-R Study Groups
 - Determines the structure of the CPM report and designates Chapter Rapporteurs
 - Assigns work to Working Parties of the Study Groups, which will conduct studies and prepare the text to be compiled in the report

Conference Preparatory Meeting, cont'd

- CPM XX-2 is held 6 months prior to the WRC
 - This meeting is open to delegates from ITU member states
 - The meeting reviews and finalizes the CPM report
 - This meeting may lead to consensus on how to address some agenda items prior to the WRC, but the meeting could produce more options for some agenda items for the WRC to consider
- The CPM Report is a contribution to the WRC

ITU-R Study Group and Working Party Output

- ITU-R QUESTION - A statement of a technical, operational or procedural problem seeking a Recommendation, Handbook or Report
- ITU-R RECOMMENDATION - An answer to a Question or part(s) of a Question which, within the scope of existing knowledge and studies, gives specifications, data, or guidance
- ITU-R REPORT - A technical, operational or procedural statement
- ITU-R HANDBOOK - Practical information engineers, system planners, and operating officials
- DRAFT CPM TEXT - Provides the technical basis, summary of studies, and suggested Methods to address WRC agenda items

ITU-R Study Groups: Main Products

ITU RADIO- COMMUNICATION SECTOR

**1,175 ITU-R
Recommendations**

**561 ITU-R
Reports**

**42 ITU-R
Handbooks**

**All these products can be download free of charge from ITU-R website
> 1 million downloads yearly**

Examples of ITU-R standards for IMT/5G and linkage with 3GPP

- ITU-R sets the guidelines and requirements which are used by 3GPP to develop standards.
- ITU-R membership is member states, industry, academia..3GPP is service providers and manufacturers.
- **IMT-2020/5G standards**
- Recommendation ITU-R M.2083-0 : IMT Vision – Framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2020 and beyond
 - Report [ITU-R M.2410](#) – Minimum requirements related to technical performance for IMT-2020 radio interface(s)
 - Report [ITU-R M.2411](#) – Requirements, evaluation criteria and submission templates for the development of IMT-2020
 - Report [ITU-R M.2412](#) – Guidelines for evaluation of radio interface technologies for IMT-2020
 - Recommendation ITU-R M.2150-2(12/2023) :Detailed specifications of the terrestrial radio interfaces of International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 (IMT-2020)**

IMT-2020 satellite component RIT development process - Working Document

Example of Radiocom Bureau's call for RITs submission Circular Letter4/LCCE/137 2 November 2023

“To Administrations of Member States of the ITU, Radiocommunication Sector Members, ITU-R Associates participating in the work of Radiocommunication Study Group 4 and ITU Academia

Subject: Meeting of Working Party 4B (e-meeting, 23 January 2024)

Working Party 4B: Systems, air interfaces, performance and availability objectives for FSS, BSS and MSS, including IP-based applications and satellite news gathering

By means of this Circular Letter, I wish to announce that a meeting of ITU-R Working Party 4B will be convened fully electronically (remote participation only / virtual meeting), on 23 January 2024. This Working Party 4B meeting will consider the acknowledgement of receipt of submissions **for candidate radio interface technologies (RITs) or a set of RITs (SRITs) for the satellite component of IMT-2020 under Step 3 of the satellite IMT-2020 process received by the 31 December 2023 deadline”.**

Status of IMT-2020 Satellite radio interface technologies

Report ITU-R M.2514-0(09/2022) Vision, requirements and evaluation guidelines for satellite radio interface(s) of IMT-2020.

Working Document Towards A Preliminary Draft New Report ITU-R M.[SAT-IMT-2020-EVAL]: Outcome of the evaluation , consensus building, and decision of the IMT-2020 satellite process(Steps 4 to7), including **Characteristics of IMT-2020 satellite radio interfaces-** (Annex 6 to WP 4BChair's report)- May 2024.

Time-table and deadlines

Extract from [Document IMT-2020-SAT/2](#)

- Step 4 is the work of IEGs (Independent Evaluation Groups)
- Cut-off for IEG Reports: Sep 2024
- Interim Report: May 2024

Steps in radio interface development process:

- Step 1: Issuance of the circular letter
- Step 2: Development of candidate RITs and SRITs
- Step 3: Reception of the RIT and SRIT submissions and acknowledgement of receipt
- Step 4: Evaluation of candidate RITs and SRITs by independent evaluation groups
- Step 5: Review and coordination of outside evaluation activities
- Step 6: Review to access compliance with minimum requirements
- Step 7: Consideration of evaluation results, consensus building and decision
- Step 8: Development of radio interface Recommendation(s)

Critical milestones in radio interface development process:

- | | |
|---|----------------|
| (1): Issue an invitation to propose RITs | September 2022 |
| (2): ITU proposed cut off for submission of candidate RIT proposals | December 2023 |
| (2): Cut off for evaluation report to ITU | September 2024 |
| (3): WP 4B decides framework and key characteristics of IMT-2020-Sat RITs and SRITs | End 2024 |
| (4): WP 4B completes development of radio interface specification Recommendation(s) | May 2025 |

Framework for 6G

- **Recommendation ITU-R M.2160-0 (11/2023): Framework** and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2030 (6G) and beyond.
- Standards, characteristics, deployment scenarios under development. Work of ITU-R WP 5D and of 3GPP.
- Working Document Towards a Preliminary Draft New Report On Development and Technology Trends for **THE Satellite Component OF IMT Towards 2030 and Beyond.**

World Radiocommunication Conferences (WRCs)

- Update the Radio Regulations
- Allocate spectrum for emerging radio services & applications while protecting existing users
- Create regulatory certainty for spectrum users, regulators, industry
- Achieve spectrum harmonization for economies of scale & equipment interoperability
- Provide a stable and predictable regulatory environment needed for future investments
- Bring together all stakeholders in a process that is aimed at building consensus

Organized every 3-4 years, last one was WRC-23 (20 Nov. – 15 Dec. 2023 Dubai, UAE)

- 3987 Participants, 163 Administrations, 151 Observers (UN Agencies, SDOs, Operators, Industries, etc.)
- > 40 agenda items, issues and topics
- 967 documents*, 6024 proposals*, 4 weeks

* see the [WRC-23 Proposal Management System](#)

The WRC Process

From ITU-R standards to WRC-27

- WRC-27 Agenda item (AI) 1.7 to consider bands 4.4-4.8 GHz, 7125-8400 MHz and 14.8-15.35 GHz for 6G.
- WRC-27 AI 1.13 for possible allocations to MSS for D2D (Direct to Device) communication in the range 694 MHz to 2.7 GHz in bands identified for IMT.
- Characteristics of 6G and of MSS will be needed for technical studies to assess sharing in compatibility of with incumbents in the bands considered under AI 1.7 (WP 5D) and under AI 1.13 (WP 4C).
- Characteristics of MSS will be needed for AI 1.13 for sharing studies.

Summary

- ITU-R process runs on approximately 4-year cycles . Work program in each SG is developed based on need for technical studies for WRC items and other priority issues
- In parallel work in SG's continues on development of standards for new technologies for IMT and the satellite component (RITs and SRITs). This activity includes input from standards bodies (3GPP, IEEE and others). Coordination with standards bodies is done as needed.
- While ITU-R Recommendations are not mandatory, unless referenced in a radio regulation provisions, they provide guidance/information for the development of national standards as well for sharing studies for WRC agenda items leading to the development of technical basis for a given WRC Cycle. WRC-27 preparations started in 2024.
- ITU-R WPs involved are 5D (Terrestrial IMT) and 4B (RIT's for MSS) and WP 4C(MSS including satellite component of IMT and D2D).

Extra Slides – Annex

Main Steps towards WRC-27

WRC-23: WRC-27 Agenda - Resolution 813 (WRC-23)

CPM27-1 (18-19 December 2023)
Results @CA/270 of 26 Jan. 2024

Council: Finalize WRC-27 agenda with dates, venue

Meetings of ITU-R WPs responsible/contributing on AIs

CPM27-2 [Dates t.b.d. for CPM Report to be available 5 months prior to WRC-27]

Final regional group meetings & national preparations
Member States' proposals to WRC-27

National and regional preparations

RA-27; WRC-27

Topics on the WRC-27 Agenda

WRC-23 agenda item 10

ITU-R WP 4A

ITU-R WP 4C

1. FSS A-ESIM & M-ESIM (47.2...51.4 GHz)
2. FSS Smaller ES Antenna (13.75-14 GHz)
3. FSS gateway ES (51.4-52.4 GHz)
4. FSS & BSS (17.3...17.8 GHz , Reg. 3)
5. NGSO FSS & MSS ES authorization
6. FSS equitable access (37.5....51.4 GHz)
7. Regulatory issues (satellite coordination & notification procedures)

- MSS NGSO-GSO space-to-space links MSS 1.11
- for low-data-rate (IoT) NGSO systems 1.12
- between 1 427 and 2 025 MHz

- MSS for IMT between 694/698 MHz and 2.7 GHz 1.13

- MSS new allocations in bands 1.14
- 2010-2025 (E-s) & 2160-2170 MHz (s-E)
- in R1&R3 and 2120-2160 MHz (s-E) in all Reg.

- 1.7 IMT identification (4.4-4.8 GHz, 7.125-8.4 GHz & 14.8-15.35 GHz)

- 1.8 RLS (231.5-275 GHz) and identification for apps (275-700 GHz)

- 1.9 RR App. 26, AM(OR)S HF modernization

- 1.10 RR Art. 21 limits for BSS, FSS & MSS to protect FS & MS (71-76 GHz and 81-86 GHz)

- SRS (s-s) allocations in several bands for lunar communications 1.15

- Protection of RAS in specific Radio Quiet Zone from NGSO systems 1.16

- MetAids (space weather) in bands between 27.5 and 614 MHz for receive-only sensors 1.17

- EESS (passive) and RAS protection 1.18

- EESS (passive) (4.2-4.4 GHz & 8.4-8.5 GHz) 1.19

ITU-R WP 5B, WP 5C, WP 5D

Note: WRC-27 agenda item numbers indicated in italic

ITU-R WP 7B, WP 7C, WP 7D

43rd CITEL PCC.II, 15 to 19 April 2024, Montevideo, Uruguay

19 specific plus the standing items, see Resolution 813 (WRC-23)